

A Combined Experimental and Theoretical Approach to Unveil the Antimicrobial Performance and Mechanism of Graphene Quantum Dots for Disinfecting Multidrug-Resistant Bacteria

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Abstract

A novel and straightforward approach to synthesis graphene quantum dots (GQDs) was developed. It followed green chemistry principles by using water as a solvent in a hydrothermal reaction and L-arginine (Arg) as a cleavage and homogeneity agent. The optimized reaction conditions allowed the formation of homogeneous nanometer-sized Arg-GQDs demonstrating excellent antibacterial and antifungal properties. Arg-GQDs were particularly active against Vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecalis* (VRE), *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus agalactiae* (GBS), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), and *Candida albicans*. Additionally, the antibiofilm efficiency of the Arg-GQDs was also investigated. Arg-GQDs promoted biofilm formation in VRE in a dose-dependent manner due to the existence of arginine residues on the surface of GQDs. Moreover, Arg-GQDs demonstrated no cytotoxic effects on L929 Fibroblast cells, maintaining up to 80 % cell viability, and showed excellent antioxidant activity. The molecular level interaction of GQDs with the Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) membrane was investigated by computational studies. The molecular dynamics simulations of the three-dimensional (3D) structure of a fragment of MRSA outer membrane identified critical tunnels and interaction-sensitive hotspots that play a key role in the antibacterial mechanism of GQDs.

Keywords: Graphene, Multi-drug resistance; Biocompatibility; Computational chemistry; Superbugs

1. Introduction

The overuse and misuse of antibiotics have led to the rise of superbugs, which pose a significant threat to global health. Infection caused by these superbugs often results in prolonged treatment, high medical costs, increased morbidity, and mortality, posing both economic and health challenges worldwide [1]. Some of these pathogens are multidrug-resistant, further complicating treatment options. As a result, researchers pay much attention to developing novel materials and coatings that can combat superbugs, particularly multidrug-resistant bacteria (MDR).

Graphene derivatives, especially graphene quantum dots (GQDs), have garnered considerable attention as a potential solution to MDR (Table S1). GQDs are highly effective against a wide range of bacteria, including both Gram-positive and Gram-negative species. They can be synthesized easily and at a large scale while demonstrating low cytotoxicity, and biocompatibility [2]. As a result, graphene-based materials have found various biomedical applications not only as antibacterial agents [3] but also for tissue engineering [4], drug delivery [5] bioimaging [6] and biosensor [7]. The size range of GQD is very broad, starting from a few nanometers, which enables them to act as highly reactive agents that can interact with the biological system at the molecular level. The structural configuration of the GQDs promotes their adherence to biomolecules like microorganisms [8]. Factors, such as size [9] surface charge [10,11], and chemical composition influence the antibacterial efficiency of GQDs [12]. The small-sized GQDs can easily penetrate the lipid bilayer of the bacterial cells and more easily interact with the DNA to induce antibacterial action [13]. Additionally, the surface properties of GQDs improve their antibacterial efficiency by enhancing their binding to the bacterial cells, leading to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [14]. The development of green and sustainable synthesis approaches is the current challenge to ensure the reproducible and scalable quality of the GQDs, as well as to understand the key molecular-level interaction of GQDs with the bacterial cell membrane.

Conventional synthesis of GQDs often involves harsh chemicals and energy-intensive processes that limit their biocompatibility and scalability [15]. The hydrothermal synthesis of GQDs is highly appreciated due to their cost-effectiveness, environmental friendliness,

and simple operational steps [16]. The use of agricultural biomass as natural precursors to fabricate GQDs not only facilitates the mass production of these nanoparticles, reducing costs but also promotes a sustainable and circular bioeconomy [17]. Various lignocellulosic biomass has been recently used to synthesize carbonaceous materials through green chemistry approaches [18]. The lignocellulosic biomass mostly consists of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and some proteins [19,20]. However, one of the challenges of employing this biomass to produce nanomaterials is breaking down the lignocellulosic structure without using any hazardous solvents or chemicals [21]. Limited studies have been reported in the literature on this aspect.

For example, GQDs were synthesized from spent green tea leaves as a carbon source using the hydrothermal method, with ethanol as a green solvent and cleaving agent [22]. In another study, nitric acid was used as a cleaving agent for lignin [23]. Choosing the cleavage agent can significantly impact the efficiency, size, and properties of the GQDs. Compared to toxic chemicals and flammable solvents, amino acids are promising modifiers because they contain multiple functional groups, such as amine and carboxyl groups, which can interact with the biopolymers during pyrolysis. During hydrothermal reactions, amino acids may act as co-catalysts and modify the conjugated area to control the aromatic condensation process. In a recent study, photoluminescent GQDs were fabricated using lignin and various amino acids [24]. Nevertheless, the specific role of amino acids in the cleavage of lignin during hydrothermal synthesis, along with the antimicrobial and biocompatibility features of GQDs has not been investigated in detail so far.

GQDs demonstrate promising antibacterial effects against MDRs. For example, the carboxyl functionalized GQDs (cGQDs) and layer-by-layer assembled (cGQDs) showed antibacterial efficacy against multi-drug-resistance *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *Escherichia coli* (E-coli) under low concentration and light illumination levels [25]. Another study demonstrates that N-heterocycle-modified GQDs penetrate the bacterial membrane, damage to the cell walls, and eventually localize at the nucleus and binding to the DNA of a broad range of MDRs and fungi [13]. Nitrogen-functionalized GQDs (N-GQDs) showed excellent antibacterial activity against a broad spectrum of bacteria. The antibacterial mechanism of the N-GQDs involved ROS and osmotic pressure

under acidic conditions [26]. These findings show that the molecular level interaction of GQDs with bacterial cell membranes is essential, and it should be investigated in detail to comprehensively understand their effectiveness against MDRs.

In this present study, wheat straw (WS) was used as a sustainable and economical carbon source in a simple one-pot hydrothermal method for synthesizing GQDs. The hydrothermal reaction was carried out in the presence of water as a solvent and amino acids such as L-arginine (Arg), L-lysine (Lys), and histidine (His) as modifiers to control the size and distribution of the resulting QDs (Scheme 1). Glycine (Gly) was used as a reference system to provide neutral pH. The antibacterial efficiency of GQDs was evaluated against a broad range of multidrug-resistant strains (MDRs). In the current state of the art, the antibacterial mechanism of GQDs against MDRs is poorly understood. To address this challenge, a detailed analysis of a three-dimensional (3D) fragment of the MRSA outer membrane was conducted. The initial structure of the MRSA outer membrane has only recently been reported by our team [27,28]. This current study expands our analysis by identifying key tunnels and empty cavities along the peptidoglycan chains. The spatial characteristics of these tunnels, including critical hydrophobicity changes throughout them, enhance our docking studies. This enabled us to identify optimal positions for small particles within the MRSA outer membrane and investigate their potential for forming complexes. The key findings of this research are highly significant, offering valuable contributions to understanding antibacterial mechanisms at the molecular level that are crucial for the further development of biomaterials to combat MDRs.

Scheme 1: A schematic of the green synthesis of Arg-GQDs, demonstrating the significance of MD calculations to explore the interactions of GQDs with the MRSA bacterial membrane at a molecular level and showing significant biocompatibility using L929 fibroblast cell line

2.1. Materials and methods

Wheat straw (WS) was harvested from an agronomy farm in Poland. Resazurin sodium salt, L-arginine, glycine, histidine, and L-lysine were purchased from Merk. Additionally, AgNO₃, NH₂OH.HCl and NaOH (analytical grade chemicals) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The fibroblast L929 cell lines were purchased from CLS cell lines service GmbH, Germany. RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with L-glutamine was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA), and LB-broth was procured from Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany). Deionized water (DW) was used in this research.

2.2. Synthesis of GQDs

At first, the WS was washed with DW to remove dust and then dried in a hot-air oven at 60°C for 24 h. The dried WS was grounded into a fine powder using a commercial mixer

grinder for 5 min at 35000 rpm. 0.7 g of powdered WS and 0.7 g of amino acid were mixed with 70 ml of DW and sonicated for 15 min. Next, the mixture was transferred into a Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated for 12 h at 200 °C in a muffle furnace. After that, the mixture was cooled down to room temperature and centrifuged for 20 min at 5000 rpm to obtain a clear solution. Finally, it was filtered by a 0.22 µm PVDF syringe filter. The obtained GQDs were further dialyzed against DW for 24 h to remove all the impurities (dialysis bag molecular weight cut-off was 3500 Da). The experiments were carried out at different hydrothermal times (4, 8, and 12 h) and temperatures (160, 180, and 200°C) to optimize the nanoparticle size and morphology.

2.3. Characterization

A high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HR-TEM, Jeol ARM 200F operating at 200 kV) was used to determine the morphology and size distribution of GQDs. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM, Tecnai G2 Spirit Twin; FEI, Prague, Czech Republic) was used to depict the dispersion of nanoparticles. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) was used to confirm the presence of functional groups. The optical characteristics were measured by photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy (FLS980 Edinburgh, UK) with an excitation source constituted by an ozone-free 450 W Xenon Arc lamp and a photosensitive element R-928 photomultiplier detector. UV-visible spectra of the Arg-GQDs were obtained using a Multiskan™ GO Microplate Spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific). Surface-plasmon extinction (SPE) spectra were recorded using Specord s600 (Analytik Jena) in 1.0 cm quartz cuvettes. Surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) spectra were acquired using a DXR Raman spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) interfaced with an Olympus microscope, employing a 4x objective with a cuvette adapter, 445 nm diode laser excitation, and 10 mW laser power. SERS spectra were measured in 10 frames with 16 s accumulation. The background of the SERS signal was removed from spectral sets using the singular value decomposition method [29]. For SERS analysis, Ag hydrosol was prepared by reducing AgNO₃ with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (NH₂OH.HCl) as described by Leopold and Lendl [30]. SERS-active systems were prepared by mixing 1 mL of Ag hydrosol with 10 µL of as-prepared solutions of GQDs or Arg-GQDs, respectively. The Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS apparatus (Malvern, UK) was used for the Zeta potential measurements to validate the existence of surface charge on the GQDs. Dynamic light scattering was used to determine the average hydrodynamic diameter of the GQDs.

The measurements were conducted on a Zetasizer Nano ZS90 analyzer using Malvern Zetasizer software 7.11 using water dispersions at 25 °C in quartz glass cuvettes with 10 mm path length. ImageJ software was used to systematically analyze Arg-GQDs sizes from the TEM.

2.4. *In vitro* antibacterial and antifungal experiments

First, the bacterial species (*S. aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Enterococcus faecalis* (VRE), *Escherichia coli* (ESBL), *P. aeruginosa PA01*, *S. agalactiae*) were cultivated in Luria Bertani (LB) broth, and *Candida albicans* were cultivated in RPMI-1640 medium (supplemented with L-glutamine) at 37 °C. The viability of microorganisms in the presence of different amounts of GQDs was determined following the “Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute” (CLSI) guidelines M27-A3 broth microdilution assay [31]. Therefore, 2.5×10^3 cells were seeded in 200 μ L liquid media in microtiter plates (flat-bottomed, 96-well, polystyrene) (Sarstedt AG & Co., KG, Nümbrecht, Germany) with and without (negative controls) different GQDs concentrations and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h with agitation at 900 rpm. Then cell viability was quantified using a resazurin assay [32]. The cells were incubated with 20 μ L of resazurin at a concentration of 0.15 mg/mL for 2 h, as living cells can reduce resazurin to the fluorescent resorufin through the production of NADPH. The equivalent amounts of produced resorufin were analyzed by fluorescence measurements at an excitation wavelength of 535 nm and an emission wavelength of 595 nm with a Tecan Infinite F200 microplate reader (Tecan, Männedorf, Switzerland).

The microbial biofilms were analyzed, as described previously [33]. In brief, again, 2.5×10^3 bacterial or yeast cells were seeded in 200 μ L liquid media in a microtiter plate (flat-bottomed, 96-well polystyrene) and incubated at 37 °C but without agitation for 24 h. The effect of the GQDs concentrations on biofilm formation was tested, and the biofilms were quantified using a crystal violet assay [34,35]. After the removal of the remaining planktonic cells, the mature biofilms were washed twice with 200 μ L of demineralized water. Subsequently, biofilms were stained with 200 μ L of a 0.1% (w/v) crystal violet solution for 15 min, the supernatant was removed, and the biofilms were again washed twice with 200 μ L demineralized water. Then, the stained biofilms were air dried for 24 h at 25 °C and destained using 200 μ L of 30% acetic acid for 15 min at 25 °C. Then, the absorbance at 560 nm was measured using a Tecan Infinite F200 microplate reader to quantify the biofilm biomass.

2.5. Cell culture studies

To determine the *in vitro* biocompatibility of the GQDs against L929 cell lines, the selected cell line was cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagles (low-glucose DEMEM), including 10 (v/v) % FBS and 100 U mL⁻¹ penicillin/ streptomycin in a CO₂ incubator at 37° C. Cells with an initial density of 0.5×10⁵ was seeded. After 24 h, the cells were treated with different concentrations of Arg-GQDs (0.005 g/L, 0.01 g/L, 0.03 g/L). The Alamar blue cell viability assay was carried out using a microplate reader at 570 and 600 nm following the manufacturer's instructions to determine the cell viability. The experiment followed the steps described above for 3 days to determine the prolonged cell viability.

2.6. Oxidative stress evaluation

The antioxidant capacity of Arg-GQDs was determined against the L929 cell lines, applying oxidative stress by hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). Cells were seeded onto 96-well plates with an initial density of 0.5×10⁵. The following day, the cell culture media was replaced with DEME + H₂O₂ (250 μM), and the cells were incubated with Arg-GQDs in two nontoxic concentrations. Then, the cell was incubated for 24 h. After a day, the Alamar blue cell viability assay was used to determine the antioxidant activity of the Arg-GQDs. Corresponding photographs of L929 were captured by optical microscopy.

2.7. Computational details

Using the peptidoglycan model [36] and insights [37], the MRSA peptidoglycan-membrane optimized structure via 300 ns molecular dynamics was used. The structure comprised 12 N-acetyl-glucosamine–N-acetyl-muramic acid disaccharides, linked by β-1-4 glycosidic bonds, with L-Ala-D-iso-Gln-L-Lys-D-Ala-D-Ala peptides cross-linked by pentaglycine. A 30×30×25 Å³ section was extracted. The system was analyzed using ChimeraX [38], and VMD [39]. Then CAVER v1.2 [40] and MOLE 2.5 [41] were used to analyze the spatial organization of peptidoglycan chains in the MRSA outer membrane, focusing on the arrangement and empty spaces between the chains. As a starting structure for GQD, the GO 1.8 graphene sheet, optimized [42] *via* molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with the GAFF2-AIM force field was selected. The selected GQD sheet had oxygen-containing functional groups covering 97.5–97.6% of the total surface area and a surface charge ranging from -17 mV/225 nm² to -17 mV/324 nm². We extracted GQD flakes from this

model consisting of 20 graphene cells and 59 carbon atoms. Functional groups were grafted onto the surface in a 2:1 ratio of hydroxyl to epoxide groups, distributed on both sides of the graphene plane. The functionalization rate was approximately 30% (18 functional groups per 59 carbon atoms), a typical value for GQD flakes. These small models underwent optimization and final refinement using the ω B97x-D [43]/def2TZVP [44] level of theory in Gaussian16 [45] with D3 dispersion corrections [46].

3. Results and discussion

The design of antibacterial GQDs with enhanced efficiency requires a fundamental understanding of the key synthesis parameters in tailoring the particle's properties and performance. By tuning the parameters of the hydrothermal method used for GQDs synthesis, we aimed to establish a correlation between the characteristics of the nanoparticles and their antibacterial activity.

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of amino acid-modified GQDs

Hydrothermal synthesis is considered one of the most potent techniques to fabricate nanomaterials with controlled size. It was shown that the presence of basic amino acid in the hydrothermal process, as a modifier, facilitated the cleavage, hydrolysis, and pyrolysis of the lignocellulosic structure of lignin. These reactions were conducted under alkaline conditions, high temperatures, and pressure. Amino acids facilitated the conversion of lignin into smaller molecular species such as monosaccharides, monophenols, and other aromatic monomers. Simultaneously, during the process of condensation polymerization and chain growth, the amino acid acted as a termination agent, reacting with active sites on the growing chains [24]. However, the specific mechanism and the role of amino acids in this context have not been well-understood so far.

**Mechanism of GQDs formation
(in the presence of Arginine)**

Scheme 2: The mechanism of Arg-GQDs formation involves hydrothermal method using water as a green solvent and amino acids a cleavage and homogeneity agent. This process includes the fragmentation of the WS under alkaline conditions, high temperature and pressure, followed by condensation polymerization, and carbonization

Within the current studies, four types of amino acids were used to reveal the effect of reaction conditions and pH on the GQDs formation and cleavage of the lignocellulose structure. The pH of the reaction mixture relates to the basic nature of amino acids, which is determined by ionizable side chains. Histidine is a basic amino acid due to its imidazole

functional group. It can be protonated in acidic conditions; however, at neutral pH, it typically exists as a neutral species [47]. Lys and Arg are basic amino acids due to the presence of amine and guanidine groups, respectively. The guanidine group in the Arg side chain makes it a strong base (Arg has a higher pKa compared to Lys) [48], ultimately, due to its strong basicity, Arg can support the formation of GQDs. Meanwhile, glycine, with only hydrogen atom in its side chain, does not have any positive or negative charge in a neutral environment. Therefore, it is unlikely to contribute to GQDs formation [49]. The TEM results of GQDs obtained in the presence of various amino acids are shown in **Figure S1**. The TEM results confirmed that Arg played a crucial role in breaking down the lignocellulose structure and facilitating GQDs formation. It can be anticipated that basic character promoted interactions of Arg with hydroxyl groups of lignocellulose-based chains and enhanced the water uptake, supporting the disintegration of the lignocellulose structure. At the same time, amine groups catalyzed the condensation reactions, as shown in **Scheme 2**. According to the TEM results, it appeared that His, Lys, and Gly did not allow control of the size and uniformity of GQDs (**Figure S1**). On the contrary, Arg-GQDs had the smallest sizes, quasi-spherical shape, and a narrow particle size distribution (**Figure 1A**). The HR-TEM micrographs of Arg-GQDs showed the nanoparticles at higher magnification and confirmed that they have quite low contrast in comparison to the supporting electron-transparent carbon film, which is typical of graphene structures (**Figure 1 B, C**) [50]. The statistical analysis showed that the average particle size of Arg-GQDs was 18.7 ± 3 nm (**Figure 1D**), while pure GQDs had an average size of 62 ± 2 nm (**Figure S2**). TEM and HR-TEM results confirmed that Arg was an appropriate modifier to control the size and uniform distribution of GQDs during the hydrothermal reaction. Since the antibacterial efficiency of GQDs is mainly influenced by their small particle size, Arg-GQDs were selected for further experiments.

FT-IR results of GQDs and Arg-GQDs are displayed in **Figure 1E**. A broad peak at 3225 cm^{-1} corresponds to the OH stretching vibration in addition to N-H groups. Another peak at 2934 cm^{-1} is attributed to the asymmetric C-H stretching due to the delignification of the lignocellulose structure. For pure GQDs, the intensity of the conjugated ketone group (C=O), is observed in the range of $1800\text{-}1100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is found to be reduced in the case of Arg-GQDs. This was ascribed to the transformation of the lignocellulose structure into

phenolic compounds, as a result of the defragmentation of the lignocellulose structure at alkaline conditions, high temperature, and pressure during the hydrothermal treatment, leading to the expansion of the π -conjugated sp^2 domain. Also, the C=O peak at 1700 cm^{-1} , detected in the GQDs, disappeared in Arg-GQDs, confirming the changes in the reactant composition during the hydrothermal process and indicating the aromatization of WS [51–53]. The peaks at 1332 cm^{-1} and 1590 cm^{-1} are ascribed to symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching vibrations of carboxylate groups in Arg-GQDs. These peaks appeared from the proton donation from COOH in a basic environment, because the addition of Arg increased the pH to 10, resulting in the formation of negatively charged ions. When the GQDs were synthesized in the presence of water, without any modifier, the cleavage and depolymerization of the lignocellulose structure were not completed, and the C=O peak at 1695 cm^{-1} was still detected. Moreover, comparing the FT-IR spectra of Arg-GQDs and raw materials confirms that Arg introduces additional functional groups such as N-H and C-N, which can be potentially used for further modifications (**Figure S4**). FT-IR spectrum of Arg-GQDs showed also peaks at 1463 cm^{-1} and 1269 cm^{-1} , corresponding to bending vibrations of C-N. This observation confirms the successful grafting of amide functional groups onto the graphitic structure.

The average hydrodynamic diameter of the Arg-GQDs dispersed in water was determined using DLS, yielding a value of about 220 nm (**Figure S5**). The difference between the values determined from DLS and TEM may be ascribed to the fact that DLS measurements were performed in the wet state, while the microscopy imaging was carried out in the dry state. Consequently, the carboxyl and hydroxyl groups present on the surface of Arg-GQDs could interact with water molecules, making them very stable and preventing any aggregation for over a month [54]. Additionally, it was concluded that the size of nanoparticles measured in the wet state encompassed not only the inner core but also the surrounding water molecules and some ions, leading to an overall increase in the hydrodynamic diameter of the GQDs.

The presence of functional groups on the nanoparticle surface influences the potential interactions of GQDs with bacterial cells, altering the charge balance on the surface of the bacterial membrane [55,56]. In the presence of water, the negatively charged carboxylate

ions (-COO-) on the surface of GQDs contribute to an overall negative surface charge. This is indicated by the negative value of zeta potential; -17 mV. When GQDs are synthesized in the presence of Arg, the positive NH₃⁺ ions partially neutralize this negative charge [57]. Consequently, the zeta potential of Arg-GQDs shifts to -12 mV. The negative charge of Arg-GQDs indicates that part of the carboxyl and hydroxyl functional groups on the surface of nanoparticles remained unaffected by Arg. These unchanged functional groups are mainly responsible for the stability of the GQDs colloids [58].

The surface features of GQDs were further characterized using SERS, (**Figure 1F**). Based on the interaction between GQDs and the surface of Ag nanoparticles, the SERS results showed significant fluorescence quenching compared to classical Raman scattering. An excitation wavelength of 445 nm was chosen to be as close as possible to the absorption bands of the GQDs to maximize the combined effect of SERS signal enhancement and molecular resonance. The improved SERS signal quality for Arg-GQDs is ascribed to their higher affinity for the surface of Ag nanoparticles and, consequently, a higher degree of aggregation, as evidenced by surface extinction spectra, (**Figure 1G**). Both GQDs and Arg-GQDs exhibited distinct D and G bands characteristic of graphene. The bands for GQDs are observed at 1380 and 1588 cm⁻¹, while for Arg-GQDs, they are detected at 1362 and 1580 cm⁻¹. The ID/IG ratios for GQDs and Arg-GQDs are similar, at 0.57 and 0.64, respectively [59].

It is known the hydrothermal reaction temperature plays a key role in the graphitization process. When the temperature is too low, incomplete graphitization occurs, leading to the formation of amorphous GQDs. Conversely, extremely high temperatures lead to the removal of functional groups [60]. Herein, the ID/IG value of Arg-GQDs formed at 200°C suggests an acceptable degree of carbon ordering and an adequate number of functional groups. XRD results revealed the presence of broad graphite peaks (002) at 21.34° (d spacing=0.39 nm) and 20.77° (d-spacing=0.36 nm) for Arg-GQDs and GQDs, respectively [61], (**Figure 1H**). This confirms that synthesized GQDs possessed a graphitic structure with a minor proportion of amorphous carbon, matching well with previous reports [60,62]. Moreover, the high interlayer distance of Arg-GQDs is attributed to the abundance of functional groups, such as carboxyl and amine groups, which was supported by the FT-IR

results. XRD of WS showed peaks at $2\theta = 15.7$ and 21.73 , corresponding to the (101) and (002) planes of cellulose, (**Figure S3**) [63].

The optical properties of the Arg- GQDs and GQDs were also studied. According to the UV-Vis analysis, (**Figure 1I**), two absorption bands were observed. The first one at 280 nm is attributed to the π - π^* transition of the graphitic sp^2 region [64], and the second one observed at 330 nm corresponds to the n - π^* transition of the C=O band [65]. The PL emission spectrum of Arg-GQDs is shown in **Figure 1J**. The results indicated that the maximum emission occurred at 534 with the excitation wavelength of 466 nm, while the maximum emission for GQDs is at 525 with an excitation wavelength of 433 nm (**Figure 1K**). Both PL peaks correspond to green light emission [66]. The observed red shift in PL correlates to the existence of amino acids in the reaction media, which, as already concluded, controls the particle size. The mechanism behind the green light emission is likely related to the size, chemical structure, and surface functionality of GQDs [67]. The particle diameter of GQDs is 62 nm, while that of Arg-GQDs is 18 nm. Those values are directly related to the quantum confinement effect and various surface chemistry, which are influenced by the existence of abundant functional groups like carboxyl, hydroxyl, and amino groups [68]. Arg-GQDs and GQDs aqueous solution showed a bright green-yellow fluorescence under UV-light illumination (Wavelength= 365 nm) (**Figure S4**). The PL properties of Arg-GQDs suggest that Arg allows control over particle size, improving the quantum confinement effect and surface functionalization. These features are essential for ROS generation, which plays a crucial in disinfecting bacterial cells.

Figure 1: Characterization of Arg-GQDs and GQDs. TEM micrograph of Arg-GQDs (A), HR-TEM micrographs of Arg-GQDs at higher magnifications (B and C), and size distribution histogram of Arg-GQDs (D), FT-IR spectra of Arg-GQDs and GQDs (E), Surface-plasmon extinction spectra of Ag/GQDs and Ag/Arg-GQDs systems (F), SERS spectra of GQDs and Arg-GQDs adsorbed on Ag nanoparticles (G), XRD patterns of Arg-GQDs and GQDs (H), UV-Vis absorption spectra of the GQDs and Arg-GQDs (I) PL spectra of the GQDs (J), and Arg-GQDs (K).

4. Antibacterial, antifungal, and antibiofilm performance

A defined set of highly prevalent pathogens, including Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (*S. aureus*, *S. mutans*, *E. faecalis* VRE, *E. coli* ESBL, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. agalactiae*), as well as the highly relevant fungi *C. albicans*, were used to analyze the antimicrobial properties of Arg-GQDs and pure GQDs. All tested nanomaterials showed excellent antimicrobial activity to a certain extent for all microorganisms. Specifically, strains such as *S. aureus*, *S. mutans*, and *S. agalactiae* are greatly affected at all tested concentrations (0.005 g/L, 0.03 g/L, 0.1 g/L). *C. albicans* and *E. faecalis* VRE also showed complete susceptibility to Arg-GQDs (**Figure 2A, B**). Overall, all strains showed significant reductions in viability after treatment with the GQDs (**Figure 2B**). *C. albicans*, as a fungal pathogen, displayed the highest susceptibility to Arg-GQDs. Both pure and Arg-GQDs exhibited significant antibacterial activity due to their unique physicochemical properties. The differences in antimicrobial activities may be attributed to the variations in the membrane structure of the bacteria, with Gram-positive bacteria being more affected than Gram-negative species. The small size and large surface area of GQDs allow them to effectively interact with bacterial cells, with surface charge and functionalization enhancing their binding to bacterial membranes. The outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria contains a lipid bilayer and lipopolysaccharides, which makes the cell wall less permeable to antibacterial GQDs. However, the small nanoparticle size facilitates the penetration of GQDs into the outer membrane, reaching the periplasmic space and cytoplasmic membrane. Additionally, the thin peptidoglycan layer beneath the outer membrane in Gram-negative bacteria is less protective compared to the thicker peptidoglycan layer in Gram-positive bacteria, which allows the GQDs to more effectively breach the cell wall and generate ROS inside the cell, leading to more severe damage. Moreover, the periplasmic space in Gram-negative bacteria provides a favorable environment for ROS accumulation, further contributing to the enhanced antibacterial activity of GQDs against these pathogens. In the case of Gram-positive bacteria, the electrostatic interaction of GQDs could facilitate the destruction of bacterial cell walls. For MDR strains, GQDs can break down extracellular polymeric substances, and block bacterial efflux pumps to induce irreversible cell damage. In addition to the damage of intracellular components, GQDs can interact with metal ions to disrupt the enzyme functions and metabolic reactions. GQDs can also generate ROS (including superoxide anions, hydroxyl radicals, and hydrogen

peroxide), which can damage bacterial cell membranes, proteins, lipids, and DNA, ultimately leading to cell death. These combined mechanisms contribute to the broad-spectrum antibacterial activity of GQDs, making them effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, fungi, and other MDR pathogens.

The intrinsic ability of specific pathogens to persist on both biotic and abiotic surfaces is a crucial feature of their virulence. By formation of so-called biofilms, bacteria, and fungi are capable of persisting in the environment in organized consortia of cells, which typically are microbial communities enclosed by an extracellular matrix formed after adherence to a certain substratum. These biofilms enhance both morbidity and mortality, as well as their physical stability to antimicrobial agents, which complicates the treatment of bacterial and fungal infections. In this context, the effect of GQDs on microbial biofilm formation was analyzed. *S. aureus*, *E. coli* ESBL, or *S. mutans* showed a significant reduction of biofilm biomasses after treatment with GQDs, while the other strains (i.e. *P. aeruginosa*, *S. agalactiae*, *C. albicans*) remained nearly unaffected with no distinct dose-dependent biofilm reduction (**Figure 2 (C, D)**). Interestingly, the pure GQDs and especially the Arg-GQDs extremely promoted biofilm formation for *E. faecalis* VRE with biofilms formed >40× as high as the untreated control cells (**Figure 2C**). Here, the GQDs and the Arg residues on their surface triggered biofilm formation in a dose-dependent manner. Further investigation is needed to clarify the molecular mechanism of promoting biofilm formation of *E. faecalis* VRE by GQDs, especially Arg-GQDs.

Figure 2: Dose-dependent inhibition of viabilities by pure GQDs and Arg-GQDs against *S. aureus*, *S. mutans*, *E. faecalis* VRE, *E. coli* ESBL, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. agalactiae*, and *C. albicans*. (A) Quantification of viable cells determined by resazurin reduction test after 24 h. The untreated control viability (100%) is represented by the horizontal line, respectively. All experiments were performed in triplicate ($N = 3$) and error bars indicate standard deviations. (B) Overview of antimicrobial activities, ranked from high activity (+++), medium activity (++) , small activity (+) to no activity (-). Anti-biofilm activity of pure GQDs and Arg-GQDs against *S. aureus*, *S. mutans*, *E. faecalis* VRE, *E. coli* ESBL, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. agalactiae*, and *C. albicans*. (C) Overview of dose-dependent activity on microbial biofilms and (D) detailed activity. The untreated control biofilm biomass (100%) is represented by the horizontal lines, respectively. All experiments were performed in triplicate ($N = 3$), error bars indicate standard deviations.

5. Cell culture studies

The high-water solubility of the GQDs prevents them from accumulating and negatively affecting cells *in vitro*, making them the safest option for biomedical applications compared to the other graphene derivatives and metal-ion-based antibacterial agents [69,70]. The cytotoxicity of Arg-GQDs was tested on fibroblast L929 cell lines at various concentrations after 24 and 72 h exposure. The results confirmed that there is no cytotoxic effect on L929 cell lines. After 24 h, Arg-GQDs with 0.005 and 0.01 g/L exhibited 85% and 87% cell viability, respectively (**Figure 3A**). The highest concentration of Arg-GQDs (0.03 g/L) resulted in a reduction of cell viability to 70 %. After 72 h, Arg-GQDs maintained the cell viability up to 80% (**Figure 3B**). It is worth mentioning that the viability assay was also carried out for pure GQDs at a concentration of 0.01g/L. After 72 h, GQDs showed toxic effects on the L929 cell lines.

The antioxidant activity of GQDs was reported in previous studies [71,72]. Based on the cell viability results, the nontoxic concentrations of Arg-GQDs were selected to determine antioxidant activity (**Figure 3C**). A dose-dependent antioxidant activity was observed. Arg-GQDs at concentrations of 0.005 and 0.01 g/L showed antioxidant activity of 86 % and 91 %, respectively, against the L929 cells. In contrast, the GQDs with a concentration of 0.01 g/L, and the control group treated with H₂O₂ (without Arg-GQDs), demonstrated a significant reduction in cell viability. As a result, Arg-GQDs exhibited significantly higher radical scavenging ($\approx 85\%$) ability compared to pure GQDs ($\approx 40\%$). The significant antibacterial and antioxidant features of Arg-GQDs highlight their importance in combating MDRs.

Figure 3: In vitro experiments: cell viability of L929 treated with Arg-GQDs and GQDs for 24 h (A), Cell viability of L929 treated with Arg-GQDs and GQDs 72 h (B). All experiments were performed six times (N = 6 and error bars represent standard deviations of the mean.

6. Computational studies

Constructing a GQD surface presents significant challenges, including the random distribution of functional groups, particularly on large surfaces, structural complexity, and the need for precise force field parameterization. The 3D structure of the GQDs of size 143x146 nm² was designed using a GO 1.8 graphene sheet optimized by Pinto *et al.* [42] through molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with the GAFF2-AIM force field. The selected GO 1.8 sheet had oxygen-containing functional groups covering 97.5–97.6% of the total surface area, with a surface charge of approximately between -17 mV/225 nm² and -17 mV/324 nm² (**Figure 4A**).

The structure of the MRSA outer membrane was only recently uncovered [36], prompting our ongoing efforts [28] to refine and analyze its properties. This study aimed to further deepen understanding of its characteristics for GQDs. Numerous compelling reasons exist to study the naturally occurring tunnels in bacterial membranes, as they play crucial roles in bacterial physiology and cellular processes. Chief among these functions is their involvement in nutrient transport into bacterial cells and removing cellular waste. The efficiency of these transport mechanisms depends on the dimensions of the tunnels and the complex interactions between the penetrating ligands. These tunnels, which act as conduits across bacterial membranes, are also central to quorum sensing, facilitating the exchange of signaling molecules between cells. Moreover, they serve as pathways for the transport of toxins and effector proteins, directly influencing the virulence of bacterial species.

A deep understanding of the evolutionary forces shaping bacterial physiology can be gained by studying biological tunnels in bacterial membranes. Our research focused on the detailed analysis of the mechanical properties, dimensions, and electrostatic characteristics of the outer membrane tunnels in MRSA. This approach aimed to unravel the structural and functional complexities of these tunnels, particularly concerning antibacterial activity against MRSA with CAVER v1.2 and MOLE 2.5 [40,41]. These tools identified 32 tunnels within a selected fragment of the MRSA membrane (**Figure 4B**), which measures 133.0 x 100.0 Å² at the base and approximately 108.0 Å in length, corresponding to the polyglycan chains. To accurately represent the membrane's electrostatic properties, naturally occurring

chloride anions and sodium cations were retained, while unbound water molecules were removed.

The extrinsic layer of the MRSA membrane features a cross-linked configuration, forming a matrix of interconnected tunnels. The analysis revealed a prominent tunnel, shown in **(Figure 4C)**, with a minimum width of 10.1 Å, sufficient to allow the free passage of small ligand molecules. This tunnel was focused on exploring the potential interactions within its structure. To this end, a detailed analysis of the hydrophobicity gradient along the tunnel ranging from -0.41 to -0.8 was conducted. This approach helped us identify key areas of increased hydrophobicity, serving as crucial reference points for a more in-depth examination of the structural properties of the constituent amino acids **(Figure 4D, E)**.

Figure 4: The 3D structure of a square GQD sheet of size $143 \times 146 \text{ nm}^2$ (A), A fragment of the studied 3D structure of the MRSA outer membrane, showing the 32 identified tunnels (B) located in the gaps between cross-linked polyglycan chains, with the largest tunnel (C) featuring a bottleneck measuring 10.1 \AA , Hydrophobicity analysis of the MRSA light tunnel (D and E)

GQDs around 1-2 nm in size are expected to penetrate the MRSA outer membrane primarily through nano-knife and insertion mechanisms [73], due to the size of the membrane tunnels (**Figure 5 (A), and (B)**). The interaction between the GQD functional groups and glycan chains in the MRSA membrane can cause membrane stiffening, impairing its normal functions and disrupting vital bacterial processes, ultimately compromising cell survival. For larger particles, membrane disruption may occur through a wrapping mechanism. The carboxyl and hydroxyl groups present on the GQD surface, along with their negative charge, enable the electrostatic interactions with bacterial cell wall components such as lipopolysaccharides and peptidoglycans. These interactions further destabilize the membrane, enhancing the antibacterial effect.

A 2 nm GQD was docked along MRSA peptidoglycan chains, with surface carboxyl and hydroxyl groups creating electrostatic attraction. However, as electrostatic contacts and dispersion forces increase, so does the likelihood of repulsive exchange interactions. The four small GQD complexes shown, docked into the MRSA structure, were selected based on the highest docking score functions. The HDOC server tool was used for this analysis, with GQDs of various sizes subjected to the default docking protocol [74].

To illustrate the scale differences, an 18 nm long and 3.3 nm wide graphene surface was also docked into the MRSA outer membrane (**Figure 5C**). This demonstration shows that GQDs of this size primarily disrupt bacteria through mechanical damage and membrane-wrapping mechanisms. In addition to their structural effects, GQDs can absorb light, typically in the near-infrared (NIR) region [75], and convert it into heat *via* the photothermal effect. This process is effective for GQDs ranging from 3 to 60 nm, making them suitable for non-invasive photothermal therapy applications (*e.g.* wound healing). Furthermore, GQDs, such as those 9.8 nm in size with a zeta potential of -28.5 mV, can generate ROS through defect-induced catalytic activity and electron transfer processes, leading to significant bacterial cell damage [76].

Figure 5: The 3D structure of four small GQDs docked at their preferred positions within the outer membrane of MRSA (A), schematic of the interactions between GQD and the MRSA membrane fragment (B), and schematic of an 18 nm long GQD fragment docked into the MRSA outer membrane (C). This configuration is unlikely to occur naturally and is shown solely to critically exclude the possibility of such an interaction.

Overall, the key factors that enhance the interaction between GQDs and MRSA include surface charge, size, and improved dispersion of the GQDs. These factors facilitate the engagement of the nanoparticles with bacterial cell membranes and biological tunnels within these membranes. The surface charge and the functional groups on the GQDs surface promote their strong adhesion to the bacterial cells. The combined experimental and theoretical findings of this study provide key insights into the molecular interactions between GQDs and the MRSA membrane, which are responsible for their antibacterial features. This fundamental understanding is beneficial to develop novel antibacterial coatings and biomaterials to combat chronic infections caused by MDRs and other superbugs. The key findings of this research are expected to advance fundamental research in antibacterial mechanisms.

7. Conclusion

Arg-GQDs were successfully applied as a new class of antibacterial and antifungal agents. Arg, due to basic character, was used as a co-catalyst and modifier, boosting the cleavage of lignocellulosic structure. As a result, nanoparticles of small size and with a high yield were obtained.

Arg-GQDs showed notable antibacterial and antifungal efficiency against various pathogens, particularly gram-positive bacteria such as *S. aureus*, *S. mutans*, *S. agalactiae*, *C. albicans*, *E. faecalis*, and VRE. The biofilm inhibitory effect of Arg-GQDs was notably significant in *S. aureus*, *E. coli* ESBL, and *S. mutans* while showing no significant effect on *P. aeruginosa*, *S. agalactiae*, and *C. albicans*. Additionally, Arg-GQDs promoted the biofilm formation of VRE. *In vitro* biocompatibility studies showed that Arg-GQDs were non-toxic at concentrations of 0.005 and 0.01 g/L, with up to 80% cell viability.

Molecular studies provided the characteristics of MRSA outer membrane, specifically its porosity and tunnels, which serve as key interaction sites for Arg-GQDs. These interactions eventually lead to the destruction of the MRSA cells. These findings lay a solid foundation for further investigation into the reaction mechanism responsible for this cell destruction.

Overall, it was concluded Arg-GQDs hold the potential for a wide range of biomedical applications, including chronic wound healing (*e.g.* diabetic, varicose ulcer, and deep-burn wounds), implant-associated infections, and other antimicrobial surface coatings to prevent the spread of infectious superbugs in hospitals and other public areas.

Supporting Information

Table S1 (Antibacterial activity of state-of-the-art graphene derivatives and Arg-GQDs); TEM micrograph (**Figure S1**) of different GQDs synthesized in the presence of various amino acids; along with the size distribution of the GQDs (**Figure S2**); FT-IR spectra for WS, Arg, and Arg-GQDs (**Figure S3**); the DLS spectra of Arg-GQDs (**Figure S4**); zeta potential measurement of Arg-GQDs and GQDs (**Figure S5**); and a photograph of the GQDs and Arg-GQDs aqueous solution under a UV light irradiation (**Figure S6**)

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization - **T.S.-S., V.K., and J.P.**, Supervision - **V.K. and J.P.**, Methodology, and data analysis and curation - **T.S.-S., V.K., J.P., A.K., A.N.K., F.R., M.S., I.S., G.N., M.K.** Investigation and original draft preparation - **T.S., A.K., A-K.K.**, Funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, resources, review and editing - **V.K., and J.P.**

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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